

The LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration

Katrin Heitmann (Argonne National Laboratory), Chihway Chang (University of Chicago), and Joe Zuntz (University of Edinburgh) on behalf of the LSST DESC

More than one thousand scientists from around the world have come together in the Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST) Dark Energy Science Collaboration (DESC) to explore the secrets of the dark Universe. Many questions demand answers: What is the cause of the late-time accelerated expansion of the Universe? Is dark energy a static vacuum energy (a cosmological constant), or does it have a dynamical component? What is its origin and how does it fit into the Standard Model of particle physics? What does the comparison between the expansion history and the growth rate of large-scale structure tell us about possible modification of General Relativity on the largest scales? What is the nature of dark matter? What happened during the very first moments of the Universe? What is the neutrino mass scale?

DESC is hoping to answer many of these questions with the unprecedented dataset to be collected by the Vera C. Rubin Observatory (Rubin). LSST will deliver data in area and depth that will dwarf what any previous cosmology survey has achieved. This highly anticipated dataset offers exciting scientific opportunities but also many technical challenges. To prepare for data arrival, LSST DESC has established a comprehensive program to investigate different cosmological probes and avoid possible systematics pitfalls from both the astrophysical and data analysis perspective, relying on simulated and precursor data.

Forecasting the power of LSST: To predict how well the data will constrain the nature of dark energy and to address the impact of a range of systematics and the requirements on how well they need to be understood, LSST DESC has undertaken a major program to forecast constraints for a dynamical dark energy equation of state, described by two parameters (w_0, w_a), where w_0 is a constant term valid for all time, while w_a describes a linear change in the equation of state (EOS) with the cosmological scale factor. LSST DESC is planning to use a range of cosmological probes: supernovae, clusters of galaxies, strong and weak lensing, and clustering of galaxies. The combination of these probes will provide the best-ever constraints on the dark energy equation of state parameters (w_0, w_a).

To fully realize the potential of LSST, DESC is busy preparing for data arrival in many different ways.

Figure 1: This figure shows the forecast for (w_0, w_a) after 10 years of LSST data taking. The black contour in the center demonstrates the constraining power of all cosmological probes combined while the red contour shows constraints from contemporary surveys. *Figure reproduced from LSST DESC 2021a [4].*

Preparing for data with simulations: In 2017, DESC embarked on an exciting endeavor to create a simulation that looks as closely as possible like the actual data to be collected by Rubin. The collaboration created a five-year synthetic survey in six optical bands covering a region of 300 square degrees in a wide-fast-deep area and a deep drilling field of approximately one square degree [1]. The simulation, named Data Challenge 2 or DC2, was set up to follow a reference LSST observing cadence, and the simulated images were processed with the LSST Science Pipelines. The DC2 sky includes variable observing conditions and CCD image artifacts as well as a range of astrophysical objects, among them lensed AGN host galaxies (Figure 2), stars in the Milky Way, and supernovae. Figure 3 shows the placement of DC2 on the sky and two zoom-ins to show the exquisite detail that was achieved in the simulation. The Deep Drilling Field is in the upper right corner of the DC2 area shown in Figure 2.

The DC2 dataset has provided many opportunities to aid the preparation for Rubin data. It has been used to test the LSST Science Pipelines, to carry out a Supernova Type Ia-

Figure 2: High-resolution (250x250 pixels, 0.04"/pixel) postage stamps of a lensed AGN host galaxy bulge (**left**) and disk (**right**). Figure reproduced from LSST DESC 2021b [1].

cosmology analysis [2], and to test LSST DESC analysis pipelines, for example. The dataset has also been made available to the larger Rubin community. As part of the Rubin Observatory Data Previews, DC2 data can be accessed by a set of “delegates” via the Rubin Science Platform (RSP), facilitating exploration of the functionalities of the RSP. And, while a synthetic sky has the advantage that all ingredients – including the nature of dark energy – are known and analyses can be validated against the known truth, data from the real Universe are as important for the preparation of data arrival.

Preparing for data with precursor data: Many aspects of the data from precursor surveys provide valuable tests for DESC analysis tools that would be challenging to achieve via simulations. Analyzing real observational data ensures that tools are up to date with state-of-the-art approaches currently deployed in the community. An additional motivation for the reanalysis projects is to bring together experts from ongoing surveys, many of whom will be working together in the Rubin era within DESC. In DESC, a coherent program has been established for performing these reanalyses, mostly from galaxy catalogs to cosmological constraints. Different projects are designed to test different parts of the pipelines. Most recently, three precursor datasets were examined — DES Y3, HSC Y1, KiDS-1000 — with an analysis focused on cosmic shear measurements [3]. Fortunately, the conclusion from the unified analysis was that the precursor datasets yield consistent results. The combined power is fairly impressive and sets a high bar for DESC endeavors in exploring the underlying cause of the accelerated expansion of the Universe. The effort motivated significant development of the DESC

software tools, to ensure that published results were reproducible.

Preparing for data via collaboration-wide challenges:

While eagerly awaiting the arrival of data from Rubin, data challenges have been one of the most productive approaches to engage members across DESC, and in the broader LSST science community, in the preparations. Casting analysis problems as competitions creates added impetus for everyone involved. For example, one step in analyzing photometric galaxy lensing and clustering correlations is tomography — splitting galaxies into approximate redshift bins based on their magnitudes. While this is usually considered a photometric redshift problem, it can also be cast as a classic machine learning problem: we want to predict labels (bins) based on features (magnitudes) with some training data (spectroscopic redshifts). In the [DESC tomography challenge](#) [5], an easy-to-use dataset and metric calculator were created, and groups were asked to submit their best code for the analysis. Twelve teams submitted 22 methods, including a wide range of machine learning approaches, and demonstrated the general tractability of the problem. In particular, several methods showed how switching to alternative target tomographic bins can greatly improve the constraining power of the result measurements but also that this was highly dependent on which science case we were considering: optimal bins for varying dark energy models were not the same as those for LCDM, for example. This has pushed DESC to think more about supporting multiple samples in our analysis process. The most effective methods that did well in multiple branches of the challenge are now

Figure 3: Data Challenge 2 (DC2) simulation region plotted on the ESO Milky Way Panoramic Image along with Subaru HSC Survey PRD2 regions. Two zoom-ins are shown to demonstrate the details and depth of the simulated dataset.
Credit: J. Cohen-Tanugi, J. Chiang

being incorporated into DESC official pipelines. Overall this “challenge” approach has been both effective and a positive experience, and DESC has used it in a range of complete and in-progress papers, including a bias modeling challenge, a competition of methods for calculating 2D spectra beyond the Limber regime, and an exploration of models for baryonic effects on small-scale matter power spectra.

The path ahead: With every report “from the summit” about Rubin getting closer to first light, the excitement in the DESC community rises. What new insights will we gain about the physics of the dark Universe, will our analysis pipelines perform at the required levels, will we be able to disentangle systematic effects from new physics, what unexpected results will Rubin deliver? DESC is preparing in many ways to take full advantage of the unprecedented data from Rubin and is

excited by the power, and the discovery potential, of LSST for cosmology.

References

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